

Study of VNTR type polymorphism (rs2234663) of the IL1RN gene encoding interleukin-1 receptor antagonist (IL1RA) in patients infected with coronavirus

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Determination of genetic predisposition to widespread diseases using molecular markers plays an important role in the prediagnosis and timely prevention of these diseases. Recently, the identification of genetic risk factors for infectious and inflammatory diseases is of particular importance in identifying groups predisposed to these diseases, and in developing special approaches to the treatment and prevention of individuals in these groups. The aim of this study was to identify the association of the VNTR type polymorphism (rs2234663) of the gene (IL1RN) encoding an interleukin-1 receptor antagonist (IL1RA) with susceptibility to infection with coronavirus and the severity of the course disease. For this purpose, 60 people who were infected with coronavirus and recovered (experimental group, EG) and 74 people who were not infected with coronavirus (control group, CG) were involved in the study. Gene polymorphism was studied by PCR method using appropriate primers. Frequencies of all alleles and genotypes detected as a result of the research were calculated. In experiments the allele *6 with the smallest size (155 bp) was not found. However, in two samples a single ~1100 bp fragment was synthesized, which compared to the known alleles corresponds to an allele containing 12 repeats. It was revealed that compared to the control the frequency of the normal allele *1 in the experimental group was ~1.5 times lower, and the frequency of the main mutant allele *2 was ~1.2 times higher. The odds ratio (OR=1.68) and relative risk (RR=1.44) values of the risk allele *2 are greater than one and are statistically significant (P=0.04). The corresponding indicators of the association of the homozygous genotype *2*2 with susceptibility to infection (OR=5.92, RR=4.93, P=0.004) also showed a significant correlation. Based on the genetic models, only the dominant model (*2*2 vs (*1*1+*2*1)) showed a statistically significant correlation (OR=6.00, RR=4.89, P=0.004). Obtained results indicate the presence of the association between the existence of the VNTR type polymorphism (rs2234663) of the IL1RN gene and the risk of coronavirus infection.

Keywords: Inflammasome, proinflammatory cytokines, interleukin, signaling pathway, receptor, agonist, antagonist, IL1RN, coronavirus, association

INTRODUCTION

Since ancient times, humanity has suffered from inflammatory diseases for various reasons. Statistical analyzes show that 3 out of every 5 deaths in the world are caused by stroke, chronic diseases of the heart as well as respiratory system, allergies, various types of cancer, obesity, diabetes, etc. (Pahva et al., 2022; <https://wonder.cdc.gov/wonder/help/ucd.html>).

Considering the large-scale historical infectious epidemics and pandemics, the number of death cases from inflammatory diseases far exceeds the proportion of other causes, including wars and natural disasters.

Inflammatory diseases include all types of damage (physical, chemical-toxic, biological) to

which the body's immune system reacts in a complex manner, a wide range of infectious/non-infectious, hereditary/non-hereditary auto-inflammatory and autoimmune diseases (for a detailed classification see: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Inflammation>).

Among these diseases, infectious diseases of viral origin, which have the ability to spread more quickly are under the great interest of researchers. The SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19) coronavirus, which broke out in Wuhan, China in 2019 and spread all over the world, is one of such viral diseases. According to the latest data, the victims of the COVID-19 pandemic exceeded 6.87 million (<https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/>).

In humans, the immune system has a complex function and regulatory mechanisms consisting of

multiple components, including innate and adaptive immunity. The molecular patterns (PAMPs and DAMPs, respectively) generated in the cytosol by pathogen exposure or damage cause the formation of a multiprotein complex of inflammasomes with pattern-recognition receptors, a key component of the immune response to inflammation, which in turn produces active forms of (pro)inflammatory cytokines (for example interleukins such as IL-1, IL-18, TNF, INF) (Gong et al., 2020; Zindel and Kubes, 2020; C.Zhao and W.Zhao, 2020, etc.).

The cascade of inflammatory responses is activated by a multiprotein oligomeric complex called inflammasome. Inflammasomes initiate the secretion of pro-inflammatory interleukins IL-1 β and IL-18. These cytokines, in turn, trigger pyroptosis, a special type of programmed cell death. Inflammasomes are expressed mainly in myeloid cells and are a major part of innate immunity. It is suggested that one of the main causes of many inflammatory diseases is the disruption of the activity/function of the inflammasome (Broz and Dixit, 2016; Effendi and Nagano, 2021).

Depending on the nature of the activators (single or double-stranded RNA (DNA), asbestos, silica, etc.), there are several classes of inflammasomes. Among them, the more widely studied are NLR subfamily inflammasomes - NLRP1, NLRP3, NLRP6, and NLRC4 (or NAIP/NLRC4, NAIP - NLR family of apoptosis inhibitory proteins). In addition, there are AIM2 (absent in melanoma 2), IFI16 (γ -interferon inducible protein), Pirin, and non-canonical inflammasomes (see: Inflammasomes. InviolveGen infocus: Practical guide, 2022). Most of these inflammasome complexes include nucleotide-binding and oligomerization domain proteins (NODs). The structure of the NLRP3 inflammasome which plays a key role in viral infections, is shown in Fig. 1.

The role of IL-1 family cytokines and signaling pathways involving the IL-1 receptor is important in the realization of the body's immune response to inflammatory processes (<https://www.sinobiological.com/research/cytokines/il1-family>).

These signaling pathways are mainly activated by kappa-B nuclear factor (NF- κ B), activating proteins (AP-1, AP-2), or mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs). A simplified scheme of the interaction of IL-1 cytokines (IL-1 α and IL-1 β) with the receptor complex is presented in Fig. 2 (Calabrese et al., 2022).

Signaling pathways associated with IL-1 family cytokines in different diseases have slightly different structures (Weber et al., 2010; Krumm et al., 2014; Herder et al., 2015; Wällberg and Clark, 2017). The

responses of the immune system during coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19) infection are reported in S.M.Vora et al. (2021) and Q.Li et al. (2022).

Fig. 1. NLRP3 inflammasome formation (simplified scheme). The monomeric NLRP3 inflammasome consists of NLRP3 (containing Nucleotide-binding oligomerization domain (NACHT), Leucine-rich Repeat (LRR) and Pyrin domain (PYD)), ASC (or PYCARD - Apoptosis-associated speck-like protein containing a CARD (C-terminal caspase-recruitment domain)), and procaspase-1 (Cap-1). NLRP3 complex consists of PYD in the N-terminus, LRR in the C-terminus, and the NACHT domains. C-terminal LRR serves as a ligand-recognition domain for other receptors (e.g. TLR) or directly microbial ligands (Seok et al., 2021).

It has been found that during the severe stage of the disease in patients with COVID-19, the level of peripheral lymphocytes significantly decreases (lymphopenia or lymphocytopenia), which leads to the progression of the disease. Two main indirect mechanisms were reported to be involved in this process. According to the first hypothesis, it is autonomous cell death due to apoptosis. Thus, in T-cells isolated from patients with a severe form of COVID-19, a higher level of caspases, the high effect of phosphatidylserine and a high rate of spontaneous apoptosis are observed (André et al., 2022).

This is strongly associated with increased levels of soluble Fas ligand in serum and high expression of Fas/CD95 in T-cells, particularly CD4+ T-cells. Therefore, in the blood serum of patients with a severe form of course, dramatically high levels of TNF- α and IFN- γ are detected in connection with a manifestation called a cytokine storm or viral sepsis. It is possible that this phenomenon is related to PANoptosis (pyroptosis, apoptosis, and necroptosis) mixed death of cells accompanied by all three cell death pathways.

Figure 2. A simplified scheme of the interaction of interleukin-1 cytokines (IL-1 α and IL-1 β) with the receptor complex, which transmits the pro-inflammatory signal to the cell nucleus. The figure also shows multiplet inhibitors of the inflammatory cascade at different levels. Symbols: Bermekimab, Rilonacept, Canakinumab, Gevokizumab, MEDI 8968 (AMG108), Anakinra (IL1RA) are monoclonal human antibodies directed against various interleukins according to the figure; IRAK 1 and IRAK 4 – interleukin-1 receptor-associated kinases; MAB-hR3 – monoclonal antibody targeting IL-1R3; MAPK – mitogenactivated protein kinase; NF- κ B – nuclear transcription factor (in B cells); TIR – Toll–interleukin-1 receptor); TRAF – tumour necrosis factor receptor-associated factor (Calabrese et al., 2022).

Interleukins are a group of natural cytokines consisting of proteins and signaling molecules expressed and secreted mainly in white blood cells (leukocytes) and a number of other - CD4 helper T-lymphocytes, monocytes, macrophages and endothelial cells. According to recent data, more than 50 interleukins and related proteins are encoded in the human genome (Brockner et al., 2010).

In particular, the role of interleukin-1 and its receptor (IL-1R) in the response to inflammation and its prevention. The IL-1 receptor consists of two

agonists (IL-1 α and IL-1 β) and one antagonist (IL-1RA). Note that the IL-1RA antagonist is a natural receptor antagonist in signaling through the IL-1 receptor (Yazdi and Ghoreschi, 2016, Fields et al., 2019). The topology of IL-1R is reported in detail by H.Schreuder et al. (1997). One of the important components of the IL-1-related signaling pathway is the IL1RN gene, localized on chromosome 2 (2q14.1), which encodes the IL-1 receptor antagonist (IL1RA) (other names of the gene: DIRA, ICIL-1RA, IL-1RN, IL-1ra, IL-1ra3, IL1F3, IL1RA, IRAP, MVCD4). The IL1RN gene consists of ~34655 bp and is transcribed in several variants (variants No. X1, X2, X3, X4, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6). These transcript variants encode the 4 so far known isoforms (intra- and extracellular) of the polypeptide [<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/3557>]. The polypeptides corresponding to the isoforms consist of 143, 159, 177 and 180 amino acid residues. The protein is mainly localized in many compartments of the cell, including the plasma membrane, extracellular fluid, cytosol, nucleoplasm, centrosome, vesicle.

Mutations of the IL1RN gene cause a rare disease called "deficiency of the interleukin-1-receptor antagonist, DIRA". For this reason, IL1RA recombinant protein is commercially produced and widely used in clinical practice under the name "anakinra" (or kineret). The polymorphism of the IL1RN gene is determined by the number of repeated copies (VNTR – variable number tandem repeats) localized in its 2nd intron (Jaiswal et al., 2012; Khazim et al., 2018,). The nucleotide sequence of the 86 bp VNTR repeat (R) located in 2nd intron of the gene is as follows (Jaiswal et al., 2012):

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ATCCTGGGGAAAGTGAGGGAAATATGG
AAATCACATGGAACAACATCCAGGAGACTC
AGGCTCTAGGAGTAACTGGGTAGTGTGC
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As a result of amplification with the appropriate primers, fragments of the following sizes are synthesized depending on the number of repeats:

- IL1RN1 (allele *1), R=4, 410 bp fragment;
- IL1RN2 (allele *2), R=2, 240 bp fragment;
- IL1RN3 (allele *3), R=3, 325 bp fragment;
- IL1RN4 (allele *4), R=5, 500 bp fragment;
- IL1RN5 (allele *5), R=6, 585 bp fragment;
- IL1RN6 (allele *6), R=1, 155 bp fragment.

The 4-repeat (410 bp, IL1RN*1 – normal allele (*1)) and 2-repeat (240 bp, IL1RN*2 – major mutant allele (*2)) alleles of the gene are more common, while the frequency of other alleles is generally ~ 5%.

Various mutations of the IL1RN gene, which encodes the interleukin-1 receptor antagonist (IL-1RA), as well as ~86 bp located in the 2nd intron of

the gene, have been reported in the literature. VNTR type polymorphism (rs2234663) is associated with various inflammatory diseases, including thrombocytopenia in children, community-acquired pneumonia, sudden infant death syndrome, acute sepsis, epilepsy syndrome associated with febrile infection, vitiligo, diabetes, knee arthritis, osteoarthritis, axial spondyloarthritis. There are many studies that show its association with rheumatoid arthritis, melanoma, febrile convulsions, repeated abortions, familial Mediterranean fever, type I and II diabetes, obesity in men, stomatitis, periodontitis, myocardial infarction, ischemic stroke, acute coronary syndrome, etc. (Highet et al., 2010; Ding et al., 2012; Nedumpun et al., 2012; Iglesias-Linares et al., 2013; Klueh et al., 2013; Sousa et al., 2013; Swellam et al., 2013; Hashemi et al., 2015; Alghamdi et al., 2017; Broer et al., 2017; Hajizadeh et al., 2017; Gabner et al., 2018; Singh et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2018; Clarkson et al., 2019; Attur et al., 2020; Osei et al., 2020; Saad et al., 2020; Tekaya et al., 2020; Abed et al., 2021; Tekcan et al., 2021; Goswami et al., 2022, etc.).

In most of these studies, the ~240 bp allele containing 2 repeats (allele *2) is noted as potential risk allele. However, there are contradictory opinions that show the association rates of a number of inflammatory diseases with allele *2 and the genotypes containing this allele vary in different populations. We have previously studied a synergistic relationship between ACE I/D and ACE2 G8790A polymorphisms in the etiology of CoVID-19 (Alibayova et al., 2022) in the Azerbaijan population.

The main goal of the current study was to determine the association of the VNTR type polymorphism (rs2234663) located in the 2nd intron of the interleukin-1 receptor antagonist (IL-1RA) gene (IL-1RN), with the susceptibility to coronavirus infection and the course of the disease.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Population studied: The material of the study was DNA isolated from blood samples collected from unrelated persons of different age groups, working in different fields. Blood samples were collected within 2022. Sample collection was carried out on a voluntary basis in accordance with international bioethical norms. For this, the relevant organizations (Public Legal Entity of the Republic of Azerbaijan "The Union of Administration of the Regional Medical Divisions", TABIB,) were addressed in advance by letter and official consent was obtained (25 April 2022). The composition of

the studied samples was as follows: (1) from people infected with coronavirus and recovered, the experimental group (EG) - 60 people (32 women, 28 men); (2) from conditionally healthy people who are not infected with the virus, the control group (CG) - 74 people (35 women, 39 men). It should be noted that the age of the studied groups varied in a wide range: in the group of patients (EG) was between 24 (1998) and 69 (1953), in the group of conditionally healthy controls (CG) ranged from 21 (2001) to 72 (1950). Blood samples were taken from persons belonging to EG after complete recovery, and information about the course of the disease was determined by questionnaire. There were 20 people who experienced the disease in an acute severe form. The control group included only individuals who tested negative for coronavirus from the beginning of the pandemic to the study period.

DNA isolation: DNA from blood samples (V=200 µl) was extracted with "Diatom™ DNA Prep 200" kit (Galart Diagnosticum, Russian Federation) according to manufacturer protocols. The amount and purity of isolated DNAs were measured in a NanoDrop 2000 spectrophotometer. The DNA samples were stored under special conditions in the refrigerator at -20°C (for a long time at -80°C) until use. DNA samples were individually diluted before PCR.

Detection of rs2234663 polymorphism of IL1RN gene: The IL1RN gene rs223466 polymorphism located on second intron was determined by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) using pairs of specific primers: Forward: 5'-CTCAGCAACACTCCTAT-3'; Reverse: 5'-TCCTGGTCTGCAGGTAA-3' (Arnalich et al., 2022; Kayar et al., 2015; Saad et al., 2020). The PCR conditions were determined by the gradient PCR. The gradient PCR was performed at 12 temperatures in the range of 45-60°C, divided equally, and 48°C was taken as the best annealing temperature of the primers. PCR reaction conditions were as follows: initial denaturation at 95°C for 5 min before the first cycle; 60 sec at 94°C (denaturation); 60 sec at 47°C (annealing); 60 sec at 72°C (elongation) - 35 cycles, and final elongation - 10 min. The synthesized fragments were electrophoresed in a 1.5% agarose gel using a 100 b.p. ladder (MBI Fermentas), visualized using ethidium-bromide staining and documented by UVITES Gel Documentation System (CS Ltd. UK).

Statistical analyses: The obtained results were statistically analyzed using the Microsoft Excel software. Odds ratio (OR), relative risk (RR), etc. parameters of alleles, genotypes and genetic models associated with susceptibility to infection/course of the disease were calculated using an online

calculator [<http://vassarstats.net/odds2x2.html>].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A total of 120 people (59 men and 61 women) were involved in the study and their genetic profiles were obtained. Figure 3 shows the electropherogram of some of the samples included in EG.

Table No1 presents the detected alleles by groups, and Table 2 presents the detected genotypes.

By summarizing the data of the genetic profiles and Table 2, the following results were obtained for both groups.

Genotypes detected in the EG group:

*2*2 – 12 people (6 women, 6 men);

*2*1 – 16 (8 women, 8 men);

*3*1 – 2 (2 women, 0 men);

*1*1 – 26 (13 women, 13 men);

*2*4 – 1 (0 women, 1 man)

*1*4 - 1 (1 female, 0 male);

*5*5 – 1 (1 female, 0 male)

~1100 AD fragment – 1 (woman)

Genotypes detected in the CG group:

*2*2 – 3 people (3 women, 0 men);

*2*1 – 26 (7 women, 19 men);

*3*4 – 1 (0 women, 1 man);

*1*1 – 37 (20 women, 17 men);

*2*4 – 2 (1 woman, 1 man)

*1*4 - 1 (1 female, 0 male);

*1*5 – 2 (1 woman, 1 man);

*2*5 – 1 (1 female, 0 male)

~1100 AD fragment – 1 (woman)

As can be seen from Table 2, in both experimental and control groups (sample No. 56 in the experimental group, sample No. 12 in the control group - both samples belong to a female person), the expected alleles of the gene were not synthesized. But instead, in both samples, a single fragment of ~1100 bp was synthesized. If compared with known alleles, this fragment would belong to an allele containing 12 repeats. In order to confirm that this fragment is indeed a population-specific allele and whether is located in the intron of the studied gene, it is necessary to sequence the fragment and determine its localization.

The frequencies of normal (*1) and mutant (*2) alleles in both studied groups, as well as in the population sample as a whole, accounted for the main part of the total frequency (~93% in EG, ~94% in CG and in the population sample as a whole) did not significantly differ. The smallest (155 bp) *6 allele was not detected during the experiment. The frequencies of other alleles (*3, *4 and *5) are ~6-7%. For this reason, we will ignore

them in future evaluations and focus mainly on the *1 and *2 alleles. Compared to the control group, in the experimental group the frequency of *1 allele was ~1.5 times lower, but the frequency of *2 allele was ~1.2 times higher.

The situation is completely different in the number of genotypes detected in the studied groups. First of all, let's note that *3*4, *1*5* and *2*5 genotypes were not found in EG. The *3*1 genotype was not observed in acute severe and severe patients. Genotypes *3*1 and *5*5 were not detected in CG. In addition, genotypes such as *2*4, *1*4* and *5*5 in patients with acute severe course, *1*4* and *5*5 in patients with severe course, *2*4 in patients with moderate course, and *2*4, *1*4 and *5*5 in patients with mild course were not detected.

This can be generally explained by the low frequency of the indicated genotypes in populations. It should be noted that the *2*2 genotype was not found in patients with a mild course. In general, the homozygous genotype of this mutant allele (*2*2) meets only ~11.2% in our population. Nevertheless, this genotype occurs ~5 times more often in the susceptible group (EG) than in the control (CG). The other two genotypes (*2*1 and *1*1) are found in our population with a frequency of ~78.3%. Compared with CG in EG the frequencies of *2*1 and *1*1 genotypes are ~1.6 and ~1.4 times lower respectively. It is interesting that the *2*1 genotype is found with high frequency (18.3%) in patients with severe acute course. But ~23.3% of patients with *1*1 genotype experienced the disease in a mild form.

In order to determine the extent to which the infection and the course of the disease are related to the presence of the *2 allele the following parameters were calculated at the 95% confidence interval (CI): the odds ratio (OR), relative risk (RR), the statistical value of the Z-test characterizing the distribution coefficient (Z-statistics) and the significance level (P) (Table 3). Calculations were performed according to the control group, and only genotypes with mutant *2 allele were taken into account.

As can be seen from Table 3, the values of the odds ratio (OR=1.68) and relative risk (RR=1.44) of the association of the *2 risk allele with susceptibility to infection are greater than one and statistically significant (P=0.04). The situation is different in the genotypes formed with the presence of the *2 allele. Although there is a fairly statistically reliable (P=0.000009) correlation, the odds ratio (OR=0.20) and relative risk (RR=0.41) values of the association of the heterozygous *2*1 genotype with susceptibility to infection are too small.

Fig. 3. Electrophoresis of selected samples belonging to persons infected with coronavirus and recovered. M – 100 bp ladder.

Table 1. Alleles revealed in the experimental and control groups

GROUPS	Alleles (amount (%))						
	*1	*2	*3	*4	*5	*6	~1100 bp
Experimental group (n=60)	71 (59.17)	41 (34.17)	2 (1.67)	2 (1.67)	3 (2.50)	–	1 (0.83)
Control group (n=74)	104 (70.27)	35 (23.64)	1 (0.68)	4 (2.70)	3 (2.03)	–	1 (0.68)
Population (n=134)	175 (65.30)	76 (28.36)	3 (1.12)	6 (2.24)	6 (2.24)	–	2 (0.75)

Table 2. Genotypes revealed in the experimental and control groups

GROUPS	Genotypes (amount (%))										
	*2*2	*2*1	*3*1	*3*4	*1*1	*2*4	*1*4	*1*5	*2*5	*5*5	~1100 bp
Experimental group (on the course of the disease)											
Acute severe	8 (13.3)	11 (18.3)	-	-	1 (1.7)	-	-	-	-	-	1 (1.7)
Severe	3 (5.0)	2 (3.3)	-	-	4 (6.7)	1 (1.7)	-	-	-	-	-
Moderatory severe	1 (1.6)	2 (3.3)	1 (1.7)	-	7 (11.7)	-	1 (1.7)	-	-	1 (1.7)	-
Mild	-	1 (1.7)	1 (1.7)	-	14 (23.3)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	12 (20.0)	16 (26.7)	2 (3.3)	-	26 (43.3)	1 (1.7)	1 (1.7)	-	-	1 (1.7)	1 (1.7)
Control group (conditionally healthy individuals)											
	*2*2	*2*1	*3*1	*3*4	*1*1	*2*4	*1*4	*1*5	*2*5	*5*5	~1100 bp
	3 (4.1)	26 (35.1)	-	1 (1.4)	37 (50.0)	2 (2.7)	1 (1.4)	2 (2.7)	1 (1.4)	-	1 (1.4)
By population											
	15 (11.2)	42 (31.3)	2 (1.5)	1 (0.8)	63 (47.0)	3 (2.2)	2 (1.5)	2 (1.5)	1 (0.8)	1 (0.8)	2 (1.5)

Table 3. Statistical parameters for the risk allele and genotypes detected in the studied group

Allele/Genotype	Odds ratio (OR, CI=95%)	Relative risk (RR)	P-value	Z-statistics
Alleles				
*1	-	-	-	-
*2	1.68 (0.98-2.86)	1.44 (0.99-2.12)	0.04	1.95
Genotypes				
*1*1	-	-	-	-
*2*1	0.20 (0.09-0.42)	0.41 (0.26-0.65)	0.000009	1.05
*2*2	5.92 (1.59-22.08)	4.93 (1.46-16.69)	0.004	2.65

Table 4. Statistical parameters for the genetic models in the studied group

Genetic models	Odds ratio (OR, CI=95%)	Relative risk (RR)	P-value	Z-statistics
Dominant *2*2 vs (*1*1+*2*1)	6.00 (1.60-22.55)	4.89 (1.38-21.41)	0.004	2.65
Recessive (*2*2+*2*1) vs *1*1	1.37 (0.67-2.83)	1.18 (0.78-1.76)	0.248	0.863
Overdominant (*1*1+*2*2) vs *2*1	1.54 (0.72-3.32)	1.16 (0.87-1.52)	0.178	1.113

On the contrary, the corresponding indicators of the association of the homozygous *2*2 genotype of the *2 allele with susceptibility to infection (OR=5.92, RR=4.93, P=0.004) indicate a fairly strong correlation. In other words, compared

to heterozygotes (*2*1), in carriers of this genotype (*2*2) the chance of infection (OR_{*2*2}/OR_{*2*1}) is ~30 times higher, and the relative risk (RR_{*2*2}/RR_{*2*1}) is ~12 times higher.

It is interesting to investigate possible genetic

models created by these alleles in the group infected with coronavirus and their association with susceptibility to infection. Thus, this allows us to estimate the potential strength of the immune system depending on the risk allele. As can be seen from Table 4, only in the dominant model the association was expressed as statistically significant ($P=0.004$). This result is consistent with the results of the association of *2 allele and homozygous *2*2 genotype with susceptibility/disease course.

Now let's consider the proportions of genotypes in dominant, recessive and overdominant (codominant) genetic models with the presence of *2 risk allele, both within separate groups and within the population sample, and analyze each of them separately.

In the dominant model with the presence of *2 risk allele, these ratios are: $*2*2/(*1*1+*2*1)=0.29$ in the EG; $*2*2/(*1*1+*2*1)=0.05$ in the CG and $*2*2/(*1*1+*2*1)=0.14$ in the population sample. The obtained values show that the probable association between the dominance of the *2 allele and the susceptibility to the coronavirus infection is ~5.8 times higher in EG than in CG, and ~2.1 times higher than in the overall pollution sample.

In the recessive model with the presence of *2 risk allele, these ratios are: $(*2*2+*2*1)/*1*1=1.08$ in the EG; $(*2*2+*2*1)/*1*1=0.78$ in the CG and $(*2*2+*2*1)/*1*1=0.90$ in the population sample. In other words, in this case, the probable association between the presence of the *2 allele and the susceptibility to coronavirus infection is not strong. Thus, the ratio is ~1.3 times higher in EG than in CG, and ~1.2 times higher than in the pollution sample.

In the overdominant (or codominant) genetic model with the presence of *2 risk allele, these ratios are as following: $(*2*2+*1*1)/*2*1=2.38$ in the EG; $(*2*2+*1*1)/*2*1=1.54$ in the CG, and $(*2*2+*1*1)/*2*1=1.86$ in the population sample. In this case, the ratio reflecting the probable relationship between the dominance of the *2 allele and the susceptibility to coronavirus infection is slightly higher in the experimental group. This ratio is ~1.6 times higher in EG than in CG, and ~1.3 times higher than in the pollution sample.

The comparison of the proportions of genotypes in all three models shows that the *2 allele or the genotype with its presence (*2*2) has a noticeable effect on susceptibility to coronavirus infection.

CONCLUSIONS

- For the first time, in the Azerbaijani population sample (infected with coronavirus and recovered – experimental group (EG), 60 people, not infected

with the virus conditionally healthy people – control group (CG), 74 people)) the VNTR type polymorphism (rs2234663) of the gene (IL1RN) encoding the interleukin-1 receptor antagonist (IL-1RA) was studied, and the frequencies of detected alleles and genotypes of the gene were determined. In experiments, in two samples (1 person in EG, 1 person in CG), instead of the known alleles of the gene, was observed a single homozygous fragment of ~1100 bp length, which corresponds to an allele containing 12 repeats compared to known alleles. In order to confirm that this fragment is indeed a population-specific allele and whether the polymorphism is located in the intron of the studied gene, it is necessary to sequence the fragment and determine its localization.

- The values of the odds ratio ($OR=1.68$) and relative risk ($RR=1.44$) of the association of the potential risk allele *2 with susceptibility to coronavirus infection were demonstrated as a statistically significant association ($P=0.04$). Analogous parameters for the *2*2 genotype showed that there is a fairly strong correlation between this genotype and the susceptibility to coronavirus infection ($OR=5.92$, $RR=4.93$, $P=0.004$). Note that compared to heterozygotes (*2*1), in carriers of the homozygous genotype (*2*2) the chance of infection (OR_{*2*2}/OR_{*2*1}) is ~30 times higher, and relative risk (RR_{*2*2}/RR_{*2*1}) is ~12 times higher. Of the genetic models, only the dominant model (*2*2 vs (*1*1+*2*1)) showed a statistically significant correlation ($OR=6.00$, $RR=4.89$, $P=0.004$).

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**İnterleykin-1 reseptoru antaqonistini (IL1RA) kodlaşdırın IL1RN geninin
VNTR tip polimorfizminin (rs2234663) tdqi**

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Molekulyar markerlərdn istifadə etməkl geniş yayılmış xəstəliklər genetik meyilliliyin myyəyn edilməsi bu xəstəliklərin preddiagnostikasında v vaxtında qarşısının alınmasında mhm rol oynayır. Son zamanlar yoluxucu v iltihabi xəstəliklərin d genetik risk faktorlarının aşkarlanması bu xəstəliklər meyilli qrupların myyəyn edilməsində, bu qruplara daxil olan şəxslərin malic v profilaktikasına xsusi yanaşmaların işlənilib hazırlanmasında xsusi hmiyyət ksb edir. Bu tdqiqatın mqsdi interleykin-1 reseptoru antaqonistini (IL1RA) kodlaşdırın genin (IL1RN) VNTR tipli polimorfizmi (rs2234663) il koronavirus infeksiyasına qarşı hssaslıq v xəstəliyin gedişatı il laqsini myyəyn etmək olmuşdur. Bu mqsdl koronavirusa yoluxmuş v sağıalmış 60 nfr (eksperimental qrup, EG) v koronavirusa yoluxmayan 74 nfr (nzart qrupu, NQ) tdqiqata clb olunmuşdur. Genin polimorfizmi uyğun praymerlərdn istifadə olunmaqla PZR metodundan istifadə olunmaqla tdqiq olunmuşdur. Aşkarlanan btn allellrin v genotiplrin tezlikləri hesablanmışdır. Eksperimentlərd n kiik lcl (155 n.c.) allel rastlanmamışdır. Lakin 2 nmunədə genin mlum allelləri vzin ~1100 n.c. lcl tk fraqment sintez edilmişdir ki, bu da mlum allellrl mqayisədə trkibində 12 tkrar saxlayan allel uyğundur. Myyəyn edilmişdir ki, nzartl mqayisədə eksperimental qrupda normal allel *1-in tezliyi ~1,5 df az, sas mutant allel *2-nin tezliyi is ~1,2 df yksk olmuşdur. Koronavirus infeksiyasına meyillilik il risk allelinin *2 laqsinin şanslar nisbti (OR=1,68) v nisbi riskinin (RR=1,44) qiymtləri birdn byk olmaqla statistik chtdn hmiyyətli (P=0,04). Homozigot *2*2 genotipinin infeksiyaya qarşı hssaslıqla assosiasiyasının mvafiq gstriciləri (OR=5,92, RR=4,93, P=0,004) d hmiyyətli korrelyasiya nmayiş etdirmişdir. Genetik modellrdn yalnız dominant model (*2*2 vs (*1*1+*2*1)) statistic hmiyyətli korrelyasiya (OR=6,00, RR=4,89, P=0,004) nmayiş etdirmişdir. Alınan nticlr IL1RN geninin VNTR tip (rs2234663) polimorfizmi il koronavirusa yoluxma riski arasında assosiasiyanın olduğunu gstrmişdir.

Aar szlr: *İnflammasoma, pro-iltihabi sitokinlər, interleykin, signal yolları, reseptor, aqonist, antaqonist, IL1RN, koronavirus, assosiasiya*